

CERN Openlab Report: CMS Heterogeneous Pixel Track Reconstruction using SYCL

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Abstract—The CMS software framework (CMSSW) has been recently extended to perform part of the physics reconstruction with NVIDIA GPUs. To avoid writing different implementations of the code for each back-end the decision was to use a performance portability library and so Alpaka has been chosen as the solution for Run-3. In the meantime different studies have been performed to test the track reconstruction and clustering algorithms on different back-ends like CUDA and Alpaka. With the idea of exploring new solutions, Intel GPUs have been considered as a new possible back-end and their implementation is currently under development. This is achieved using SYCL, that is a cross-platform abstraction C++ programming model for heterogeneous computing. It allows developers to reuse code across different hardware and also perform custom tuning for a specific accelerator. The SYCL implementation used is the Data Parallel C++ library (DPC++) in the Intel oneAPI Toolkit. In this report, we will present strengths and weaknesses of this heterogeneous programming model as well as the performance of a physics reconstruction algorithm (clustering) on different hardware.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the High-Luminosity phase of the LHC (HL-LHC) the accelerator will reach an instantaneous luminosity of $710^{34} cm^{-2} s^{-1}$ with an average pileup of 200 proton-proton collisions. This will lead to a computational challenge for the online and offline reconstruction software that have been developed. To face this complexity CMS has decided to use heterogeneous computing, meaning that different types of architectures will be used instead of CPUs only.

To accomplish this task, before the start of Run-3 the CMS experiment has equipped the HLT nodes with NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPUs that are currently used in production for:

- pixel unpacking, local reconstruction, tracks and vertices
- ECAL unpacking and local reconstruction
- HCAL local reconstruction

This choice has resulted in higher throughput thanks to the use of accelerators and better physics performance due to the fundamental redesign of the algorithms to fully exploit the parallelism capabilities of GPUs.

The goal for the HL-LHC is to offload at least 50% of the HLT computations to GPUs in Run-4 scaling up to 80% in Run-5.

Currently, the code to be executed on GPUs is written in CUDA specifically for NVIDIA GPUs. Through a custom-built compatibility layer, the same code can run entirely on CPUs, if no GPU is available. In this way, to offload the computational work on different non-CPU resources, different

implementations of the same code are required. This approach should be avoided because it would introduce code-duplication that is not easily maintainable. A possible solution is the use of **performance portability libraries**, that allow the programmer to write a single source code which can be executed on different architectures (Figure 1).

The CMS experiment has evaluated some performance portability libraries and Alpaka has been chosen for Run-3. The migration from CUDA to Alpaka at the HLT will be performed in the next few months. Despite this, studies on this kind of libraries are still ongoing and other solutions are being explored. One possibility is to use Data Parallel C++ (DPC++), an open-source compiler project developed by Intel, that is part of the oneAPI programming model. DPC++ is based on SYCL, a cross-platform abstraction layer maintained by Khronos Group that allows code to be written using standard ISO C++ both for the host and the device in the same source file.

At the moment DPC++ officially supports CPUs, Intel GPUs and Intel FPGAs. The support for NVIDIA and AMD GPUs is in active development and possible to use them with the Intel's LLVM Compiler.

Fig. 1: Cross-architecture Compiling

II. PIXELTRACK STANDALONE

A. Overall Structure

Pixeltrack is a heterogeneous implementation of pixel tracks and vertices reconstruction chain, starting from the detector raw data, creating clusters, then n-tuplets that are fitted to obtain tracks and at last those are used to reconstruct the

Fig. 2: Pixeltrack Reconstruction Steps

vertices. In Figure 2 above, we show the overall structure of the algorithm as well as what happens on Host (CPU) and on Device (i.e. GPU).

B. This work - Clustering Algorithm

In Figure 3, with yellow color you can see the result of the clustering. These are clusters of nearby pixels on the silicon layers. The purpose of this algorithm is to topologically cluster active pixels with related energy deposits. This problem is known as "connecting the dots", its very combinatorial and massively benefits from parallelization. Hence implementing it to run on GPUs will increase its performance.

Fig. 3: Clustering Algorithm

Fig. 4: DPCT tool workflow

III. MIGRATING FROM CUDA TO SYCL

A. Data Parallel Compatibility Tool (DPCT)

The Intel® DPC++ Compatibility Tool is part of the Intel® oneAPI Base Toolkit. The goal of this tool is to assist in the migration of an existing program that is written in CUDA to a program written in SYCL and compiled with the DPC++ compiler. This tool generates SYCL code as much as it can. However, it will not migrate all code and manual changes are required. As seen in Figure 4 we used dpct tool as a starting point from the already written CUDA implementation.

B. Overall Differences

The main differences that we encountered can be summarized as following:

- 1) For all memory operations and kernel launch the **queue** is needed. A queue in SYCL is created and associated with each available device (equivalent to a CUDA stream).
- 2) Different terms and different meanings in the thread hierarchy (work-item, work-group vs thread and blocks etc.).
- 3) Shared memory with accessors and SYCL multi-pointer implementation

C. Memory Allocation and transfer

In the following array we can see the different APIs used in SYCL regarding memory.

CUDA	SYCL
cudaMalloc()	malloc_device()
cudaMemset()	memset()
cudaMemcpy()	memcpy()
cudaFree()	free()

TABLE I: CUDA vs SYCL - Memory operations

malloc_device(): device allocations that can be read from or written to by kernels running on a device, but they cannot be directly accessed from code executing on the host. Data must be copied between host and device using the explicit USM memcpy mechanisms.

free(): free memory allocated with Malloc functions.

memcpy(): copy memory between host and device.

memset(): set memory allocated with Malloc functions.

copy(): copy memory from src to dest.

D. Execution Model - Thread Hierarchy

CUDA	SYCL
Stream Multiprocessor (SM)	Compute Unit (CU)
SM core	Processing Element (PE)
thread	work-item
block	work-group
grid	ND-range

TABLE II: CUDA vs SYCL - thread hierarchy

The SYCL execution model exposes an abstract view of GPU execution. The SYCL thread hierarchy consists of a 1, 2, or 3-dimensional grid of work-items. These work-items are grouped into equal sized thread groups called work-groups. Threads in a work-group are further divided into equal sized vector groups called sub-groups (see Figure 5).

Work-item: A work-item represents one of a collection of parallel executions of a kernel.

Sub-group: A sub-group represents a short range of consecutive work-items that are processed together as a SIMD vector of length 8, 16, 32 etc.

Work-group: A work-group is a 1-, 2-, or 3-dimensional set of threads within the thread hierarchy. In SYCL, synchronization across work-items is only possible with barriers for the work-items within the same work-group.

ND-range: An nd-range divides the thread hierarchy into 1, 2, or 3-dimensional grids of work-groups. It is represented by the global range, the local range of each work-group.

E. Atomics

Since the algorithm that we ported makes use of atomic operations, we needed to have the corresponding implementation in SYCL. Atomic operations are available as members of the **atomic_ref** class. Consider the following code:

```
// atomic_ref
atm = sycl::atomic_ref<>(addr[0]);
// atomic operation
atm.fetch_add(operand);
```

As seen in SYCL you have to define an **atomic_ref** and then you can do most of the atomic operations (add, sub, max, min, compare_exchange_strong, compare_inc). For the **atomic_ref**

one has to pass as templated parameters, **address_space**, **memory_scope** and **memory_order**. We explain the possibilities and the meaning of the most important ones:

```
enum class address_space : /* unspecified */ {
    global_space,
    local_space,
    constant_space, // Deprecated in SYCL 2020
    private_space,
    generic_space
};
```

Fig. 6: address_space options

```
enum class memory_scope : /* unspecified */ {
    work_item,
    sub_group,
    work_group,
    device,
    system
};
```

Fig. 7: memory_scope options

We use global and local space in atomics that operate on global or local variables accordingly (Figure 6). For the memory scope we use *device* when we want to have atomics between groups (blocks in CUDA), and *work_group* when we want atomics within a group (block in CUDA) as shown in Figure 7.

F. Shared Memory

Since the algorithms written in CUDA were using shared memory, that was the case with SYCL as well. With SYCL you have 2 options for using shared memory:

- **Accessor** declaration for the shared variables *outside* the kernel,
- SYCL **multipointer** extension *inside* the kernel (more CUDA-like)

We attach a code snippet for the **multi_ptr** implementation from the extension which is the one we ended up using:

```
var_shared=group_local_memory_for_overwrite
<type>(item.get_group());
```


Fig. 5: SYCL thread hierarchy

We did not use the accessor implementation because when we have a lot of shared variables in a kernel the host code was becoming verbose and hard to follow.

IV. RESULTS

The porting of the complete pixeltrack algorithm is still ongoing, but we are able to successfully run the code both on Intel CPUs and Intel GPUs. For this 2-month Openlab program we managed to:

- 1) Successfully develop the SYCL implementation of the data transfer from host to device as well as the clustering algorithm,
- 2) Run the same code on both CPU or GPU or both in hybrid configuration,
- 3) GPU has 1.4x speedup w.r.t. CPU,
- 4) All different configurations with the same code.

V. CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, heterogeneous computing can be a solution to face the computational challenge and a compatibility layer will help in reproducibility of the results and code maintainability. SYCL is promising from this point of view and the first tests show really good performance, but it's not yet ready for a full-scale implementation since some features are still under development.

VI. REFERENCES

pixeltrack-standalone [git repo](#)
pixeltrack-standalone [paper](#)
Porting CUDA to SYCL
DataParallel C++